
Working paper

**The Assessment
of the State of the Digital Economy
in South-East Asia**

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Working paper WP2

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Abstract

This paper presents a thorough analysis and assessment of the state of the digital economy in Southeast Asian countries. Based on data from 10 countries belonging to the ASEAN association, taken from the ITU database, specialized agency for information and communication technologies (ICTs), and covering the period from 2017-2022, research was carried out according to a new, pioneering and original approach for the ITU data and indicators which is presented in a methodology part of the article. The basis for conducting empirical research was, first of all, an analysis of the literature on the subject, which showed the meaning and importance of key factors in the digitization process of ASEAN countries. Then, expert selection of data was made and an innovative approach in a methodology was developed for determining the main synthetic indicator CMG, as well as partial synthetic indicators. A taxonomic similarity clustering study was performed to assess the structures of the digitization level of ASEAN countries and finally focused on the clustering method.

Key findings resulting from the conducted research emphasize the significant differences occurring not only in the level of socio-economic development but also in the level of digitalization of individual countries in the ASEAN region, which allowed the separation of individual groups in the form of the so-called clusters. Among the ASEAN countries, groups of countries with high, medium and low levels of digitalization were distinguished compared to the entire region. The obtained research results largely confirmed the presumptions that among the countries in the ASEAN region can be observed dependence that countries characterized by high levels of GDP, degree of industrialization and social development simultaneously belong to countries with high levels of digitalization.

The prepared article and the results of the conducted research fill the identified research gap and undoubtedly constitute a significant contribution to the development of research on the level of digitalization of economies in ASEAN countries, thus constituting added value in the field of economic and management sciences.

Keywords: digitalization, ASEAN region, similarities and differences of the countries, method of taxonomic grouping of structures, the type of clustering.

1. Introduction

Changes observed in the world economy since 2013¹ are called the fourth industrial revolution or digital revolution. In this context, the term “Economy 4.0” which is based on the development of digital technologies and their wide application, is characterised by the networking of participants in social and economic life and the so-called datafication, i.e. the integration of data downloaded from these networks. At the same time, the transformation of

¹ In 2013 the final report of the working group operating in Germany was published, dealing with, among others, the preparation of recommendations in the field of intelligent industry. The term industry 4.0 (German: “Industrie 4.0”) comes from the high technology strategy project of the German government and was first used during the international Hannover Messe fair in 2011.

Working paper WP2

business models and strategies is observed. The revolution 4.0 is not only a grass-roots business-industrial initiative but a revolution requiring the integration of horizontal and vertical ties in the aspect of added value chains and production systems (Gótz, 2018). The business sector has a very important role in this revolution. The fundamentals for entities' functioning and development are connected with the environment created by the State.

In this scope, the “State” has a special place as one of a distinctive features of the region it concerns, combining political, social and economic phenomena that integrate – in the light of understanding the idea of the state – three fundamental components (Klima, 2009): territory, law or government, embodying authority and power, population (society).

In this paper, the research was undertaken to identify factors enabling the development of digitalization of economies in ASEAN countries², currently creating the “world's largest free trade area”, and constituting a group of 10 countries with a population exceeding 600 million people and an estimated USD 100 billion in revenues from the digital economy in 2023, which is growing at 27% CAGR since 2021 (Yu, 2024). The clear digital transformation of ASEAN countries is evidenced by data showing that in 2015 the digital economy of this region accounted for 1.3% of ASEAN’s GDP and in 2019 already 3.7% with the assumed 8.5% in 2025 (Yu, 2024).

Despite the above-mentioned positive changes in general in the digitalization of the ASEAN countries, at the detailed level, certain differences and disproportions between these countries are observed. For this reason, the aim of this article is to analyse and assess the digitalisation levels of Southeast Asian countries together with an indication of their similarities and differences, and to present the relevant conclusions and inferences arising therefrom.

This scientific article is divided into several parts which are logically interconnected and systematized (according to the key of scientific cognition processes, including analysis and synthesis, deduction and induction, comparison and contrast and also generalization and conclusion). It contains:

- 1) this Introduction
- 2) the Literature review - as a theoretical part of the research
- 3) The Methodological part of the research
- 4) the Empirical part of the research and
- 5) the Conclusion part.

² This author of the research (Yu, 2024) confirms the existence of three sets of factors influencing the development of digitalization of the economies of ASEAN countries:

- 1) national factors relating to policy at the national level
- 2) regional factors relating to other Asian countries, including China, but even outside Asia, such as cooperation with the USA
- 3) global factors.

Research has confirmed that factors at the national level are decisive because they enable the rapid development of peripheral innovations such as the ASEAN region, **while factors at the regional and global levels are of an auxiliary nature.**

Working paper WP2

2. The digital economy and digital transformation of ASEAN countries: a literature review

The digital economy includes all those economic processes, transactions, interactions, and activities based on digital technologies (Schilirò, 2022). The digital economy is an ecosystem where consumers, businesses, and governments exist within a digital society, engaging and creating value that benefits all stakeholders (Schilirò, 2022).

The transformation towards economy 4.0, i.e. a digitalized economy, requires both bottom-up and top-down actions, including (Recommendations, 2013³):

- 1) establishing a regulatory and legal framework that takes into account controversial issues of data protection, legal liability, and trade restrictions (e.g., cryptographic components built into many devices that are the subject of exchange and are classified as dual-use goods). Necessary adjustments are also required in the business area (cooperation guidelines, templates of contracts, agreements and audits);
- 2) standardization and reference architecture (integration within chains and networks of many entities, while ensuring a uniform set of norms, guidelines, standards and reference frameworks);
- 3) ensuring security: product reliability, appropriate quality, but also the workplace – working conditions (safety), data transmissions and information confidentially (security);
- 4) ensuring appropriate infrastructure, such as broadband networks and high-quality, reliable connections, with the expansions of broadband networks being crucial not only within the home country but also between countries/ partners;
- 5) management of complex systems (including planning, developing models explaining processes and their supervision. This requires appropriate methods, techniques and tools for designing such models and developing plans);
- 6) work design and organisation. Employee tasks are changing and are evolving towards real-time supervision, coordination and evaluation, and sometimes assisting devices;
- 7) training and professional development of employees, related to continuous training, improving qualifications, and gaining experience in the workplace;
- 8) resource efficiency. There is a need for a reliable valuation and comparison of the potential benefits that the 4th industrial revolution brings due to savings in materials and energy, with the costs that it generates due to the necessary expanses in new technologies, advanced machines, factories, etc.

In particular, the actions of the State, as the guarantor of the safety and security of the rights and freedoms of the individual, but also of society as a whole, seem to be of great importance. Digital economy is closely linked to digital society, as the infrastructure created within the economy is the basis for the creation of a digital society (Kovac et al, 2023). The

³ In this study, the authors systematized these activities according to the degree of their importance from the point of view managing the economy 4.0 in the light of the state's obligations as the creator of rules, principles and law.

Working paper WP2

digital economy is also defined as the contribution of any economic transaction involving both digital products and digital industries to GDP (Asian Development Bank, 2021).

In contemporary discussions about the digital economy, there is a strong focus on the dynamic environment of Southeast Asia. The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) is a rapidly growing trade bloc consisting of ten member countries: Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Lao PDR, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. With a total population of over 680 million, more than half of whom are under 30 years old and a combined GDP of nearly USD 3.2 trillion in 2019, ASEAN stands as the third-largest regional economy in Asia and the fifth-largest globally, trailing only the US, China, Japan, and Germany (Isono and Prilliadi, 2023; ASEAN, 2022). ASEAN is among the world's fastest-growing regions, with average real GDP growth projected to reach 4.6% in 2023 and 4.8% in 2024. By 2030, it is expected to become the fourth-largest economy globally. This growth is fuelled by a population of 700 million, consisting of young, educated, increasingly online individuals and a burgeoning middle class (Lee, 2024).

Table 1. GDP per Capita in ASEAN countries in the years 2017-2022 (in USD)

Country	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Brunei Darussalam	28,806.1	30,642.1	26,462.1	26,462.1	32,383.0	37,445.9
Cambodia	1,402.4	1,539.8	1,685.7	1,588.9	1,637.2	1,758.0
Indonesia	3,880.1	3,937.2	4,200.4	3,922.1	4,357.0	4,777.5
Lao PDR	2,472.3	2,585.0	2,627.8	2,630.1	2,586.8	2,022.0
Malaysia	9,965.2	11,079.7	11,228.3	10,400.1	11,475.6	12,448.0
Myanmar	1,152.0	1,246.6	1,223.8	1,280.1	1,317.7	1,093.2
Philippines	3,134.1	3,261.2	3,512.0	3,329.3	3,576.2	3,623.5
Singapore	61,174.4	66,823.5	66,068.1	61,298.1	77,679.7	82,794.0
Thailand	6,745.5	7,470.8	8,297.1	7,648.2	7,751.9	7,494.4
Vietnam	2,983.5	3,250.5	3,464.9	3,552.0	3,716.8	4,109.1
ASEAN	4,446.3	4,720.1	4,971.9	4,677.3	5,095.0	5,391.8

Source: ASEAN Secretariat (2023).

In 2022, the manufacturing sector was the largest contributor to ASEAN's GDP, generating US\$767 billion, which accounted for 21.2% of the total GDP. This was followed by the trade sector (14.7%), public administration and other services (10.3%), agriculture (9.8%), and real estate and business activities (6.9%). The remaining industries collectively contributed 33.8%, with net taxes on products adding another 3.3%. Notably, the accommodation and transportation industries experienced the highest growth rates in 2022, with increases of 23.8%

Working paper WP2

and 16.0% respectively, reflecting a robust recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic's impact. During the peak of the pandemic, these industries were significantly affected due to lockdown measures (ASEAN Statistical Brief, 2024).

The manufacturing industry is the leading sector in many ASEAN countries, contributing 27% of GDP in Thailand, 25.4% in Myanmar, 24.8% in Vietnam, 23.4% in Malaysia, 21.6% in Singapore, and 18.3% in Indonesia. In contrast, the agriculture, forestry, and fishing sector dominate in Cambodia and Lao PDR, accounting for 22.2% and 17.8% of their GDPs, respectively. Brunei Darussalam's economy is heavily reliant on the mining and quarrying sector, which makes up 43% of its GDP, while the wholesale and retail trade sector is the primary contributor to the Philippines' economy at 18.1% (ASEAN Statistical Brief, 2024).

Since 1997, ASEAN has been engaged in digital transformation efforts, starting with the adoption of ASEAN Vision 2020, which introduced an initiative focused on advancing information and communication technology (ICT) development in the region (Suranto et al, 2023). Southeast Asia is also home to a rapidly expanding population of digital natives thriving in an exceptionally innovative environment (Murphy, 2022). Enhanced ICT infrastructure along with a tech-savvy demographic advantage, are the primary catalysts for economic growth in ASEAN (Aryani, Andari, and Suhindarto, 2022). According to the e-Conomy SEA 2022 study conducted by Google, Temasek, and Bain & Co., ASEAN had 460 million Internet users as of 2022. Remarkably, 100 millions of these users joined within the past three years. By the end of 2022, it's projected that 370 millions of these Internet users will transition into digital consumers, meaning they will purchase products and services through online channels.

This region, marked by its diverse socio-economic landscape and rapidly advancing technological infrastructure, offers a complex policy environment filled with both challenges and opportunities. The growing digital economy in Southeast Asia is underscored by multifaceted considerations encompassing technological innovation, regulatory frameworks, and socio-economic dynamics. For ASEAN countries, the digital economy is essential for driving digital transformation. The digital transformation of ASEAN countries presents immense opportunities for economic growth and development. Digitalization initiatives in Southeast Asia countries are motivated by various factors. The primary aim is to boost economic growth and enhance competitiveness globally. These efforts focus on nurturing digital industries, attracting investments, and creating job opportunities (Suranto et al, 2023).

In this context, digital transformation refers to the comprehensive integration of digital technology into all facets of business, fundamentally altering how businesses operate and deliver value to customers. The use of digital transformation between countries is also reshaping global trade through the innovation of electronic commerce (e-commerce) as a market platform for businesses across and within countries as well as in logistics, inventory, ICT, and payment systems (Ing and Markus, 2023).

The impact of digital products, often referred to as “digital technologies”, can be categorized into three levels of integration: digitization, digitalization, and digital

Working paper WP2

transformation. Although these terms are often used interchangeably in the literature, recent reviews indicate that they should be seen as sequential phases (Kraus et al., 2022). Digitization refers to the shift from analog to digital information, digitalization involves how digital technologies alter business processes, and digital transformation represents the broader organizational change driven by digital technologies, resulting in new or revised business models (Kraus et al., 2022).

In details, *digitization* refers to the process of converting data into a digital format (Verhoef et al., 2021). Literatures also define digitization as the transformation of analog tasks into digital formats (Li et al., 2016; Sebastian et al., 2017; Horváth and Szabó, 2019) or the integration of IT into existing processes. More broadly, it is seen as the cost-effective creation (Lai et al., 2010) or facilitator of cost-effective resource configurations utilizing IT (Vendrell-Herrero et al., 2017).

Secondly, *digitalization* refers to the incorporation of digitized data into established production processes to achieve higher efficiency (Burkett, 2017). According to Verhoef et al. (2021), digitalization relies heavily on IT to create new business opportunities by revolutionizing established processes such as communication, distribution, and business relationship management.

The third is *digital transformation*, which is similar to digitalization except that it refers to a more extensive integration of digital products, such as a large enterprise involving hundreds of employees and tools in its strategic use of digital technologies (ADB, 2021). Digital transformation establishes a new business model by employing innovative business logic to generate and capture value (Verhoef et al., 2021; Pagani and Pardo, 2017). Moreover, digital transformation leverages digital technologies to facilitate cross-border interactions with suppliers, customers, and competitors (Singh & Hess, 2017; Verhoef et al., 2021).

Digital transformation is also linked to increased economic growth and productivity. For instance, a data by the Asian Development Bank (ADB) indicates that digitalization could contribute an additional USD 1 trillion to ASEAN's GDP by 2025 (ADB, 2021). The value of ASEAN's digital economy is projected to double to USD 2 trillion by 2030, driven by the Digital Economic Framework Agreement (DEFA) (ASEAN Indonesia, 2023). This projection underscores the significant economic impact digital technology can have on the region, driven by advancements in digital infrastructure, technology industries, and digital services in education, finance, governance, and health. The ADB emphasizes the need for targeted investments and new partnerships to build capacity and skills, create an enabling environment for entrepreneurship, and promote inclusive growth across the region. Companies such as Expedia, Go-Jek, Grab, Meta, Netflix, Lazada, and Sea Group are expected to expand their teams by 10% annually as they continue their core operations. This growth rate significantly outpaces the general employment growth of 1%–3% in most Southeast Asian countries. Additionally, job opportunities for flexible workers are projected to triple by 2025 (Tobing, 2022).

Working paper WP2

Digital transformation has accelerated due to the challenges posed by COVID-19 (Srisathan & Naruetharadhol, 2022), which have spurred digital-enabled innovation globally, including in the ASEAN countries (Srisathan & Naruetharadhol, 2022; Muhamad et al., 2021). Despite a slowdown in 2022, according to Bloomberg, Southeast Asian tech start-ups raised approximately \$8.2 billion in 2020, and ASEAN had over 30 unicorns—start-ups valued at \$1 billion or more—by 2021 (Marsan, 2022). However, a significant concern in ASEAN's digital transformation is the growing digital divide both within and across countries (Ing and Markus, 2023). The digital divide, initially understood in a dichotomous way as a state of having or not having access to ICT, is treated today as a complex and multidimensional phenomenon (Cruz-Jesus et al., 2012, Vassilakopoulou & Hustad, 2021). The digital divide, once seen as a simple binary issue of having or not having access to ICT, is now regarded as a complex and multidimensional phenomenon (Cruz-Jesus et al., 2012; Vassilakopoulou & Hustad, 202). Recent literature on the digital divide identifies three main types of divides: the access divide, related to access and equipment issues; the usage divide, associated with digital literacy; and the performance/capacity divide, linked to the benefits of using ICTs, particularly the Internet (Aissaoui, 2021).

Southeast Asia struggles to close the digital divide, marked by unequal access to and use of information and communication technologies (ICTs). This gap, affecting connectivity, access, usage, and skills, hinders the region's fast economic growth and technological advancement. Although Singapore and Malaysia have high internet penetration and digital literacy, countries like Laos, Cambodia, and Myanmar still face limited internet access and low digital skills. Moreover, there is a significant disparity in digital technology access between urban and rural areas in these nations (Suranto et al, 2023).

Fig. 1. Mobile Phone Density in ASEAN countries in the years 2013-2022

Notes: Cellular/Mobile Phone density (per 100 persons); ASEAN data for 2020-2021 is estimated as the data for some AMS are not available.
Source: ASEAN Secretariat (2023).

Working paper WP2

The capability of technology deployment is crucial for digital transformation, especially given the uneven deployment due to limited capabilities. ASEAN countries exhibit various digital divides, as highlighted by Ing and Markus (2023), including disparities in internet speed, usage, and technology production. According to Speedtest in 2022, Indonesia's internet speed is 21.95 Mbps. Singapore leads with 211.36 Mbps, while Cambodia (19.31 Mbps) and Myanmar (18.35 Mbps) have the lowest speeds in ASEAN.

Internet usage in ASEAN varies significantly: high-income countries have nearly 90% internet users, whereas lower middle-income countries have about 45%, and low-income countries less than 21% (Ing and Rodrik, 2022). Brunei Darussalam has the highest usage at 95%, followed by Singapore (92%) and Malaysia (89.6%). Myanmar (35.1%) and Lao PDR (33.8%) have the lowest usage rates (World Bank, 2021).

Fig. 2. Internet Services Density in ASEAN counties in the years 2013-2022

Note: Internet subscriptions per 100 persons; ASEAN data for 2020-2021 is estimated as the data for some AMS are not available.

Source: ASEAN Secretariat (2023).

In terms of technology production, high-income countries had an average of 19,000 patent applications from 2016 to 2020, compared to about 1,500 in lower-middle-income countries and fewer than 100 in low-income countries. In ASEAN, Singapore had 1,778 patent applications in 2020, followed by Indonesia with 1,309. Thailand (863), the Philippines (476), and Brunei Darussalam (5) had the fewest applications (World Bank, 2021).

The digital divide should be measured periodically to monitor progress and determine continuous improvement (Wati, Caplanova, Darmo, 2024). In Indonesian context for example, Wati, Caplanova, Darmo (2024) highlights significant disparities in digital skills across its

Working paper WP2

provinces, particularly between more developed urban areas and remote, rural regions. Such factors as socio-economic status, education, geographic location, and cultural attitudes play a crucial role in shaping individuals' access to and proficiency in digital technologies.

Strengthening regional cooperation through initiatives like the ASEAN Digital Integration Framework will be crucial. ASEAN's digital integration is the use of digital and digital economy to enhance regional trade, growth, competitiveness and inclusiveness, and to achieve a stronger, more connected and resilient community. This effort encompasses enhancing interoperability, developing digital infrastructure, building human resource capacity, and establishing national legal and regulatory frameworks. The goal is to accelerate economic growth at both the regional and national levels (Isono and Prilliadi, 2023). ASEAN's digital integration involves harmonizing digital regulations, promoting digital innovation, developing digital skills and literacy, improving cybersecurity, increasing access to affordable and quality internet, and enhancing e-commerce and e-services (Hendratmoko, 2023). The adoption of emerging technologies such as AI, blockchain, and IoT can further accelerate digital transformation. Integrating digital solutions for sustainability, such as smart grids and sustainable urban planning, will also be vital for the region's future.

Despite notable strides, disparities persist in policy formulations across the region, thereby engendering a fragmented landscape marked by regulatory incongruities and varying levels of digital infrastructural development. Consequently, discerning the gaps within extant policy frameworks becomes imperative in fostering a cohesive and conducive environment for digital economic advancement. While significant progress has been made in the ASEAN, challenges such as the digital divide, cybersecurity, and regulatory issues need to be addressed. Continued investment in digital infrastructure, skills development, and regional cooperation will be essential for realizing the full potential of digital transformation in the ASEAN region.

Research dedicated to the issue of digitalization in Southeast Asia has been conducted. In a working paper entitled "State of Digitalization in the Southeast Asia Region," Suranto et al. (2023) examined a bibliometric analysis of the state of digitalization in Southeast Asia, focusing on the period from 2018 to 2023. By leveraging the Scopus database, this research conducted a comprehensive review of literature in the digital domain, identifying key trends, regional disparities, and thematic focuses within the ASEAN nations.

A similar study was conducted at the country level. Wati, Caplanova, and Darmo (2024) elaborated on the digital divide across Indonesian provinces based on the 2022 Indonesian Digital Society Index (Indeks Masyarakat Digital Indonesia/IMDI) published by the Ministry of Communication and Informatics. It also analyzed key factors of the digital divide using data from the Indonesian Bureau of Statistics and a multiple linear regression model. The results identified three types of digital divides across Indonesian provinces related to access, usage, and outcomes of information and communication technology. Gross Regional Domestic Product per capita, wage/salary, proportion of formal labour, and size of the working-age population were identified as factors significantly affecting the digital divide.

Working paper WP2

However, research dedicated to the digitalization levels of Southeast Asian countries and the identification of structural similarities is very limited. Therefore, this research aims to fill this gap.

3. Methodology

3.1. The research procedure and assumptions of the scientific work

The implementation of scientific research on “The Assessment of the State of the Digital Economy in Southeast Asia” involved the following activities and actions, allowing it to be carried out, by adopting the following research procedure:

- 1) firstly, it was necessary to outline the research area and the title of the paper and to conduct a preliminary analysis of the literature on the subject,
- 2) then the need to formulate basic research assumptions was identified, including:
 - identification of the research gap,
 - formulation of the research problem,
 - determination of the objective of the scientific work,
 - determination of the subject, object, temporal and spatial scope of the planned empirical research,
 - formulation of research hypotheses,
- 3) The next step of the research procedure was a proper analysis of the literature on the subject, providing the basis, the foundation, so to speak, for conducting the empirical research. This part of the paper presents certain conclusions and inferences from the literature review, emphasising the importance of factors described as driving forces in the process of digitalisation in the ASEAN countries, while drawing attention to certain differences in this respect between the countries in the aforementioned region.
- 4) The selection of the research method and the selection of adequate data necessary to be used within the framework of the indicated research method, together with the presentation of research limitations.
- 5) Implementation of the empirical research.
- 6) Formulation and presentation of conclusions.
- 7) Indication of possible areas for future research.

The lack of research dedicated to the issue of digitalisation level of Southeast Asian countries together with the identification of similarity of structures in this regard were identified as the **research gap**. To fill the research gap thus identified, the choice was made to use clustering within cluster analysis as part of the statistical methods, which makes it possible to divide groups of countries into so-called superior and inferior clusters.

Working paper WP2

The **research problem** was formulated in the form of the following question: *Are the digitalisation levels of Southeast Asian countries similar or are there specific differences between them and, if so, are they significant?*

With the research gap thus identified and the research problem formulated, the authors of the paper defined the **objective of this research paper**, which is to analyse and assess the digitalisation levels of Southeast Asian countries together with an indication of their similarities and differences, and to present the relevant conclusions and inferences arising therefrom.

The **subject of the research** relates directly to its objective defined above and that is to analyse and assess the digitalisation levels of Southeast Asian countries.

The **object of the research** includes the following Southeast Asian countries:

Brunei Darussalam,
Cambodia,
Indonesia,
Lao PDR
Malaysia,
Myanmar (Burma),
Philippines,
Singapore,
Thailand, and
Vietnam,

which together form one region centred around the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN).

The **spatial scope of the research**, on the other hand, takes into account the spatial-geographical location of the aforementioned ten countries which form one region and whose countries belong to the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN). It is worth mentioning at this point that the objectives behind the creation and development of ASEAN include:

- economic aspects: to accelerate economic growth in the region,
- social and cultural aspects: social progress and cultural development in the region,
- legal and security aspects in the region: to promote regional peace and stability through abiding respect for justice and the rule of law in the relationship among countries in the region and adherence to the principles of the United Nations Charter.

The choice of the ASEAN countries was not random, but is related to their importance and the role they play in the global economy. It is a region with a population of 686 million as of 2024 – i.e. more than 8% of the world's population, real GDP growth of 4.6%, i.e. 4.08 thousand billions of US dollars in current prices, which is just under 4% of the GDP share of

Working paper WP2

the world economy in 2024. [<https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/profile/SEQ>, <https://aseanaustralia.pmc.gov.au/sites/default/files/asean-cef.pdf> 18.06.2024].

The strength of these countries is their dynamic economic development which began at the turn of the 1990s, making them the so-called “Asian tigers” that not only pursue intra-regional cooperation, but meet the needs and opportunities in this respect through cooperation with countries in Europe, America, the rest of Asia, Australia and other regions of the world.

It is worth noting at this point that in 2020, the foreign ministers of the European Union and ASEAN countries decided to elevate cooperation between the EU and ASEAN to the level of a strategic partnership [<https://pism.pl/publikacje/perspektywy-rozwoju-partnerstwa-strategicznego-ue-asean>, 18.06.2024], which, also in the European context, speaks in favour of conducting scientific research in the horizon of mutual cooperation and development of scientific thought between scientists from these regions.

The **temporal scope of the research** covers the period between 2017 and 2022, which was adopted due to the availability of data in the topic of analysis and assessment of digitalisation level of the analysed economies of the ASEAN countries.

In the study, the following research hypotheses (RHs) were formulated:

RH1: The Southeast Asian (ASEAN) region is characterised by significant diversity not only in terms of the level of socio-economic development but also in terms of the digitalisation level of individual countries in this region, which makes it possible to distinguish particular groups of them in the form of so-called clusters.

RH2: Among the ASEAN countries, groups of countries with high, medium and low levels of their digitalisation are distinguished from the region as a whole.

RH3: Among the countries in the ASEAN region, a correlation can be observed that countries characterised by high levels of GDP, degree of industrialisation and social development simultaneously belong to countries with high levels of digitalisation, these are: Malaysia, Singapore and Brunei; while countries characterised by low levels of GDP, degree of industrialisation of the economy and social development, such as Vietnam, Laos and Cambodia, belong to countries with low levels of digitalisation.

3.2. Methods, sources of data and limitations of the research

With reference to the research method, a choice of taxonomic clustering of similarities was made to assess the structures of digitalisation level of the ASEAN countries. In this respect, the choice concerned the clustering method which consisted of:

- division of the data into groups containing elements that are similar to each other, i.e. have common features, in other words overlapping,
- close to a given k-means distance,
- generated from a similar distribution, and

Working paper WP2

- minimising disorder, i.e. entropy.

Taking into account the chosen research method, which is in line with the adopted objective of this paper and other conceptual assumptions, a selection of data was made, which will be used for calculations using the aforementioned research method. For this purpose, data were collected from the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) database. ITU is the United Nations specialised agency for information and communication technologies (ICTs), which, in terms of the thematic aspect of the research, provides the substantive justification for this choice. It should be mentioned that the ITU database includes a total of 178 indicators.

For the purposes of this research paper, a division was made into three base research areas which were named:

- 1) Connectivity Area
- 2) Markets Area
- 3) Governance, Affordability, Sustainability and Trust Area (GAST Area).

Finally, following the selection of available data in the database according to the aforementioned selection rules for the ASEAN countries, 23 indicators were selected through expert selection, including:

- 8 for Connectivity Area,
- 8 for Markets Area and
- 7 for the GAST Area

The next step was to develop a main synthetic indicator, called **CMG indicator** (named after the first letters of the area names). The CMG Indicator is the measure enabling the hierarchy of economies according to the three areas:

- Connectivity Area (C),
- Markets Area (M),
- Governance, Affordability, Sustainability and Trust Area ($GAST$).

The general form of the indicator is as follows:

$$CMG_i = w_1 C_i + w_2 M_i + w_3 GAST_i$$

where the components C_i , M_i and $GAST_i$ denote the values of sub-indicators for the i - country, respectively.

Linear ordering according to the standardised sums method was used to determine the sub-indicators C_i , M_i and $GAST_i$. The procedure for estimating sub-indicators is as follows:

1. Selection of diagnostic variables (x_{ij}).
2. Determining preferences regarding variables, i.e. which of the diagnostic variables is:
 - stimulant,
 - destimulant,
 - nominee.
3. Bringing all the variables into the stimulant form

Working paper WP2

4. Determining the weights (w_j) for diagnostic variables.
5. Standardization of variables (z_{ij}).
6. Determining the maximum and minimum values of standardized variables:

$$z_{0j}^+ = \max_i z_{ij}$$

$$z_{0j}^- = \min_i z_{ij}$$

7. Determining the value q_i for the standardized sum method:

$$q_i = \sum_{j=1}^m w_j z_{ij}$$

8. The above should be done separately for each group of variables constituting individual sub-indexes
9. Determination of sub-indicators based on the formula:

$$C_i = \frac{q_i - q_0^-}{q_0^+ - q_0^-}$$

$$M_i = \frac{q_i - q_0^-}{q_0^+ - q_0^-}$$

$$GAST_i = \frac{q_i - q_0^-}{q_0^+ - q_0^-}$$

where $q_0^+ = \sum_{j=1}^m w_j z_{0j}^+$ and $q_0^- = \sum_{j=1}^m w_j z_{0j}^-$.

10. Determination of the indicator:

$$CMG_i = w_1 C_i + w_2 M_i + w_3 GAST_i$$

where w_i is the weight assigned to the i -th sub-indicator ($\sum w_i = 1$),
where: $w_1, w_2, w_3 = \frac{1}{3}$

11. Creating a ranking of facilities

Both the C_i , M_i and $GAST_i$ sub-indicators, as well as the general CMG_i indicator, have values from 0 to 1. The value 0 means the lowest position in the ranking, while the value 1 means the highest position in the ranking.

The following diagnostic variables were used in the study:

- A. **Connectivity Area** (8 indicators):

Working paper WP2

1. Households with a computer (% of households that have a computer. A computer refers to a desktop computer, a laptop (portable) computer or a tablet (or similar handheld computer). Weighted: 0,05
 2. Households with Internet access at home (% of households with Internet access at home. Access can be via a fixed or mobile network. If one member of the household has a mobile phone with connection to the Internet and makes it available for all members, then it should be considered that the household has access to the Internet). Weighted: 0,2
 3. Fixed-telephone subscriptions (Refers to the sum of all active analogue fixed-telephone lines, voice-over-IP (VoIP) subscriptions, fixed wireless local loop (WLL) subscriptions, ISDN voice-channel equivalents, fixed public payphones and satellite-based subscriptions provided to fixed locations that allow for a voice communication). Weighted: 0,05
 4. Mobile-cellular subscriptions (Refers to the number of subscriptions to a public mobile-telephone service that provide access to the public switched telephone network (PSTN) using cellular technology. It includes the number of postpaid subscriptions and the number of active prepaid accounts). Weighted: 0,1
 5. Population coverage, by mobile network technology. Weighted: 0,1
 6. Fixed-broadband subscriptions (Refers to fixed subscriptions to high-speed access to the public Internet (a TCP/IP connection), at downstream speeds equal to, or greater than, 256 kbit/s divided by population and multiplied by 100; per 100 people. Weighted:0,1
 7. Active mobile-broadband subscriptions (Refers to the sum of active handset-based and computer-based (USB/dongles) mobile-broadband subscriptions that allow access to the Internet). Weighted: 0,1
 8. Individuals using the Internet (Refers to the proportion of individuals who used the Internet from any location in the last three months. Access can be via a fixed or mobile network); (in %). Weighted: 0,3
- B. Markets Area** (8 indicators):
1. Wireless Local Loop (status: Full competition (year when competition was introduced); Monopoly; Partial competition (year when competition was introduced). Weighted: 0,12
 2. Local fixed line services (status: Full competition (year when competition was introduced); Monopoly; Partial competition (year when competition was introduced). Weighted: 0,12
 3. Mobile Broadband (status: Full competition (year when competition was introduced); Monopoly; Partial competition (year when competition was introduced). Weighted: 0,14
 4. Annual investment in telecommunication services (Annual investment in telecommunication services refers to the investment during the financial year made by entities providing telecommunication networks and/or services (including fixed, mobile and Internet services, as well as the transmission of TV signals) for acquiring or upgrading fixed assets (usually referred to as CAPEX), less disinvestment owing to disposals of fixed assets). Weighted: 0,14
 5. National broadband plan exists (status: Yes, No). Weighted: 0,14

Working paper WP2

6. Revenue from mobile networks (Revenue from mobile networks refers to retail revenue earned from the provision of mobile-cellular communication services, including all voice, SMS and data (narrowband and broadband) services offered by mobile operators offering services within the country during the financial year under review), value in USD. Weighted: 0,12
 7. Revenue from all telecommunication services (Revenue from all telecommunication services refers to revenue earned from retail fixed telephone, mobile-cellular, Internet and data services offered by telecommunication operators (both network and virtual, including resellers) offering services within the country during the financial year under review. It includes retail revenues earned from the transmission of TV signals, but excludes revenues from TV content creation), value in USD. Weighted: 0,12
 8. Full-time equivalent telecommunication employees (Full-time equivalent telecommunication employees refers to the total number of persons, in full-time equivalent (FTE) units, employed by telecommunication operators in the country for the provision of telecommunication services, including fixed-telephone, mobile-cellular, Internet and data services). Weighted: 0,1
- C. Governance, Affordability, Sustainability and Trust (GAST) Area (7 indicators):**
1. Consumer protection authority (status: Yes, No). Weighted 0,15
 2. ICT Policy (status: Yes, No). Weighted 0,15
 3. Regulatory framework for e-Applications (status: Yes, No). Weighted 0,15
 4. Individuals with ICT skills, Finding, downloading, installing and configuring software. (Refers to the proportion of individuals with ICT skills, defined as having undertaken certain activities in the last three months, independent of the device(s) used. Individuals can have carried out multiple activities and therefore be considered to possess several ICT skills). Weighted 0,1
 5. Individuals with ICT skills, Writing a computer program using a programming language. (Refers to the proportion of individuals with ICT skills, defined as having undertaken certain activities in the last three months, independent of the device(s) used. Individuals can have carried out multiple activities and therefore be considered to possess several ICT skills). Weighted 0,15
 6. ICT consumer protection legislation (status: Yes, No). Weighted 0,15
 7. Cybersecurity legislation/regulation exist (status: Yes, No). Weighted 0,15

Only quantitative variables were used to determine sub-indicators. Binary variables (Yes/No) were recoded into dummy variables. Any missing data were supplemented using data imputation method: linear interpolation and the k-NN (k-Nearest Neighbours).

The next step of the methodology procedure was adopting the clustering method. To classify countries in terms of the similarity of the value and structure of the new, created “CMG indicator”, a cluster analysis was used as one of the basic methods of so-called unsupervised grouping (Borowiecki, Siuta-Tokarska et al., 2021).

Working paper WP2

Cluster analysis is a set of methods of multidimensional statistical analysis, used to extract homogeneous subsets of objects of the study population, which helps to find groups of so-called clusters of objects based on variables that characterize the analyzed objects and this method uses measures of discrepancy or distance between objects when forming clusters (Borowiecki, Siuta-Tokarska et al., 2021). By applying the Ward method, clusters of ASEAN-10 countries were formed using CMG data for both 2017 and 2022—with forming clusters in each year and showing it by dendrograms, presented in the form of figures. The choice of countries to represent each cluster was driven by the components of the CMG values and its internal structures consisting of the following indexes: Connectivity, Market and GAST. It is worth explaining that the most direct way to calculate the distance between objects in a multidimensional space is to calculate the Euclidean distance, however, often in this analysis a different metric can be taken as a measure of distance. The chosen method is considered to be the most effective, although it aims to create clusters of small size (Stanisz, 2007). The selection of the number of clusters is based on the difference between the maximum similarity within the groups and the minimum (Kaufman, Rousseeuw, 1990). On this basis, an optimal number of concentrations of three was established.

The limitations of this research are connected above all with the limitations of the methods which were used in this research - they are described in detail in the literature on the subject of statistical methods (Pociecha, Podolec, Sokołowski, Zając, 1988; Evans, 2008; Ott, Longnecker, 2021) and also with the limitations of the data in the ITU database – the lack of completeness.

This research on the topic of digitalisation levels of the ASEAN countries, with its analysis and assessment, inference and presentation of conclusions based on data from the ITU database, selected through expert selection, together with the development of a synthetic main indicator and synthetic partial indicators, is clearly of a pioneering nature, which is also confirmed by the earlier review of the literature on this topic area.

4. Results and discussion

The ITU indicators, which are collected in the ITU database correspond to the development of the digital economy and society, impacting the standard of living and economic competitiveness in the ASEAN. The authors of this publication chose ITU database indicators for the following reasons:

- this database contains not only quantitative but also qualitative measures which is very important in the context of the methodology approach and allows for a reduction of measurement error and a higher quality of the research,
- this database does not only contain some indicators but also their grouping in critical areas from the point of view of digitalization issues;

Working paper WP2

- this database enables time comparison of the indicators for a given economy, and countries' areas as well as comparison of countries in the world between them in the years and periods.

Based on data from the ITU database, an appropriate measurement was made in terms of the newly created proprietary “CMG” indicator and its partial sub-indicators: Connectivity, Market and GAST.

The authors adopted two main research years: 2017 and 2022 which show a difference of 6 years of the above-mentioned indicators, which, taking into account the time range and the development of digitalization in the world, illustrates a specific degree of these changes. In Fig 3 the ASEAN countries' values of CMG indicator and its sub-indicators are presented.

Fig 3. ASEAN countries' values of the CMG indicator and its sub-components

Source: authors own analysis.

The data presented in Figure 3 indicate the existence of certain similarities, but also differences between the countries of the ASEAN group. Comparing the results for individual ASEAN countries over time (in 2017 and in 2022), for some of them there is an improvement in the value of the main CMG indicator and its sub-indicators and for others a decrease in their

Working paper WP2

value. This illustrates that despite belonging to one geographical, socio-cultural and civilization region such as ASEAN countries, their development including its level, directions and dynamics of changes in their digital transformation, are not the same. In order to better and deeper analyze this area, the clustering method for ASEAN countries is prepared. In fig 4 the hierarchical clustering analysis is presented.

Fig 4. Dendrogram for the ASEAN countries based on CMG indicator and its sub-indicators in 2017

Source: Authors own analysis.

The hierarchical clustering analysis, shown in figure 4, represents the degree of the CMG sub-indicators, measuring the global development of ICTs at the level of access, uses, and skills in various ASEAN countries in 2017.

Based on Ward's method with squared Euclidean distances, the clustering of countries was provided with a priori cluster structures based on CMG sub-indicators. The dendrogram clearly identified three clusters. Cluster 1, consisting of Brunei Darussalam, Malaysia, and Singapore, showing the relatively higher similarity probably because of advanced ICT development and similar policies. Cluster 2, consisting of Indonesia, Philippines, Thailand, and Viet Nam with moderate similarity and at different levels of ICT development. Cluster 3, composed of Cambodia, Lao P.D.R., and Myanmar, formed lower independent group probably

Working paper WP2

due to their relatively lower ICT development and different socio-economic factors. Consequently, the clustering shows the different extents of socio-economic development and competitiveness among ASEAN countries in the year 2017.

In figure 5 the same analysis – clustering - for 2022 is prepared.

Fig 5. Dendrogram for the ASEAN countries based on CMG indicator and its sub-indicators in 2022

Source: Authors own analysis.

The hierarchical clustering in Figure 5 for the year 2022, indicating the level of ICT development in ASEAN countries. Applying Ward's method using squared Euclidean distances for the countries under study, three distinct clusters are shown. Cluster 1 represents the countries Malaysia and Philippines, with high similarity probably due to their ICT development and similar policies. Cluster 2, consists of Indonesia and Myanmar with moderate similarity and a balance of ITC characteristics. Cluster 3 is the most diverse and includes Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Lao P.D.R., Singapore, Thailand, and Viet Nam, which represent a broad spectrum of socioeconomic conditions, from probably the most developed economy in the sample such as Singapore to some of the least developed, such as Cambodia and Lao P.D.R. Therefore, this clustering enables us to make inferences concerning the relative ICT development and competitiveness levels among these countries in the year 2022.

Working paper WP2

Fig 6. Comparative Cluster Values of the CMG and its sub-components in ASEAN countries in 2017 and 2022

Source: Authors own analysis.

Figure 7. Value of the CMG indicator and its sub-components in a cross-section of isolated clusters for ASEAN countries in 2017 and 2022

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3
In 2017	Brunei Darussalam Singapore Malaysia	Indonesia Philippines Thailand Viet Nam	Cambodia Lao P.D.R. Myanmar
CMG	0.6874	0.5986	0.2324
Connectivity	0.8106	0.4499	0.1467
Market	0.4158	0.6609	0.1022
GAST	0.8359	0.6849	0.4482
In 2022	Malaysia Philippines	Indonesia Myanmar	Cambodia Lao P.D.R. Thailand Viet Nam Brunei Darussalam Singapore
CMG	0.6065	0.4748	0.4978
Connectivity	0.6440	0.3084	0.6101
Market	0.2554	0.5659	0.2425
GAST	0.9200	0.5799	0.6406

Source: Authors own analysis.

Working paper WP2

Additionally, as shown in figure 6 and 7, the hierarchical clustering for 2017 and 2022 points to changes in the ICT development landscape of ASEAN countries. The clustering structure shows more variation in 2022, indicating the changes in the ICT metrics for ASEAN region. According to these shifts, there could be changes in economic policies or development programs and even external factors that might impacted the socio-economic conditions. While in 2017, there were more distinct clusters in the analysis; in 2022, countries at different levels of development blended as one block, which could be an indication of growing integration or changing policy impacts. This dynamic clustering underlines the need for further continuous monitoring and adaptive policies to foster balanced regional development. Additionally, the figures also indicate the convergence of clusters in 2022, while in 2017 the variation is highly heterogeneous.

The country-level analysis of the CMG indicator has outlined several changes between the two surveyed years. These changes are positive and show an increase in the CMG development. In the analyzed years, three of the teen ASEAN countries had below-average, while seven countries were above average in the ASEAN. Countries below the average, both in 2017 and 2022, were Cambodia, Lao PDR., and Myanmar. In 2017, the lowest country-level of CMG score was by Lao PDR., with 0.1225 points, while in 2022, it also was Lao PDR. with a slight increase to 0.3093 points. Countries with above-average CMG values in both years included Brunei Darussalam, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Thailand, Vietnam, and Singapore. As shown in Table 2, comparing the performance of individual countries against the ASEAN average in 2017, it was found that Lao PDR. had the lowest rate of 23.7%, while Singapore had the highest 147 % rate. Similarly, in 2022, it was found that Lao PDR. had the lowest rate of 60.1 %, while Singapore had the highest 137.9 % rate.

Table 2. Summary of the CMG measure and its sub-indicators with the lowest-highest values compared to the ASEAN average in 2017 and 2022

Lowest-Highest Country Scores as a % of the ASEAN Average That Year		Included:		Difference [P.P.]	Degree of Recorded Differences	Assessing Changes in Implementing Convergence Processes
		Lowest Values [%]	Highest Values [%]			
Connectivity	2017	3.6	93.2	89.5	Degree 2	+
	2022	13.8	97.0	83.2		
Market	2017	1.3	94.8	93.5	Degree 3	+
	2022	1.0	62.9	61.8		
GAST	2017	31.9	87.9	56.0	Degree 1	+
	2022	48.0	100.0	52.0		
CMG	2017	12.3	75.8	63.6	-	+
	2022	30.9	71.1	40.1		

Note: Clarification: Degrees 1-4 represent the magnitude of differences between 2022 and 2017, with degree 1 being the smallest and degree 4 the largest. A "+" indicates positive changes enhancing convergence, while a "-" indicates negative changes reducing convergence.

Source: Authors own analysis.

Working paper WP2

The fact that the gap between the lowest and highest rates as compared to the ASEAN average has been gradually decreasing from 63.6 pps in 2017 to 40.1 pps in 2022, gives a positive trend toward more convergence across ASEAN countries. This positive trend is further diluted by the countries' observation where the value of the ratio between the highest and the lowest rates dropped from 6.2 in 2017 to a far lower value of 2.2 in 2022.

Table 3 shows the trend in average CMG values and its sub-indicators from 2017 to 2022 in each clusters. The findings on CMG development in these clusters are conclude as following:

- For 2017, the CMG in Cluster 1 was 0.6874 points, which after five years, by 2022, reached 0.6065 points, a decrease of 11.7 % . The values of CMG in Cluster 1 for 2017 and 2022 remained above than the ASEAN average.
- For 2017, the CMG in Cluster 2 was 0.5986 points, which after five years, by 2022, reached 0.4748 points, a decrease of 20.6 % . The values of CMG in Cluster 2 for 2017 remained above, while for 2022 remained near the ASEAN average.
- For 2017, the CMG in Cluster 3 was 0.2324 points, which after five years, by 2022, reached .4978 points, an increase of 114 % . The values of CMG in Cluster 3 for 2017 remained lower, while in 2022 remained almost the same as the ASEAN average.

Table 3. Dynamics of average CMG and its sub-indicators in 2017–2022 (2017 = 100%)

Cluster Number	Connectivity	Market	GAST	CMG
1	91.78	84.57	104.03	95.29
2	89.52	95.21	94.89	93.66
3	310.49	191.51	128.63	176.13
Average ASEAN	109.57	86.90	101.91	100.15

Source: Authors own analysis.

The average CMG increased only in the 3rd cluster. For cluster 1, it almost decreased by 5%; on the other hand, cluster 2 decreased by 6.5%. While cluster 3 increased by 76%, putting Clusters 3 in positions of great momentum between the years 2017 and 2022.

Connectivity

The sub-components of the CMG indicator also present interesting findings. As such, Connectivity in 2022, show an increase of 19.2% compared to 2017, however its average is below the average value of the aforementioned CMG. Further, as presented in figure 3, the countries with the highest growth rates were Lao P.D.R., Viet Nam, Philippines, Cambodia, Thailand. However, Myanmar experienced negative growth.

In 2017, six countries were below the ASEAN average. These countries included Cambodia, Indonesia, Lao P.D.R., Myanmar, Philippines, and Vietnam. Whereas in 2022 it was three countries such as Cambodia, Lao P.D.R., and Myanmar. The lowest scores on the connectivity indicator in the ASEAN Member States for 2017 appeared in Lao P.D.R. with 0.0361 points, Myanmar with 0.199, and Cambodia with 0.2052. While in 2022, it was Myanmar with 0.1381 points, Cambodia with 0.2596, and Lao P.D.R. with 0.2643.

Working paper WP2

Significantly, for all of those countries which had the worst connectivity rates in 2017, their scores against the ASEAN average improved by 2022 except for Myanmar.

Conversely, in 2017, four countries were above the ASEAN average. These countries included Brunei Darussalam, Malaysia, Singapore, and Thailand. Whereas in 2022 it was 7 countries, such as Brunei Darussalam, Indonesia, Philippines, Vietnam, Malaysia, Singapore, and Thailand. The highest scores on the connectivity indicator in the ASEAN Member States for 2017 appeared in Singapore with 0.9315 points, Brunei Darussalam with 0.7759, and Malaysia with 0.7244. While in 2022, it was Singapore with 0.9696 points, Brunei Darussalam with 0.8122, and Malaysia with 0.7919. Significantly, for all those countries which had the highest connectivity rates in 2017, their scores against the ASEAN average improved by 2022.

Thus, as shown in table 2, comparing the performance of individual countries against the ASEAN average in 2017, it was found that Lao P.D.R. had the lowest rate of 7.7%, while Singapore had the highest 181 % rate. Similarly, in the 2022, it was found that Myanmar had the lowest rate of 26.5 %, while Singapore had the highest 189 % rate.

The fact that the gap between the lowest and highest rates as compared to the ASEAN average has been gradually decreasing from 89.5 pps in 2017 to 83.2 pps in 2022, gives a positive trend toward more convergence across ASEAN countries. This positive trend is further diluted by the countries observation where the value of the relationship between the highest and the lowest rates dropped from 23.6 in 2017 to a far lower value of 7.1 in 2022.

Table 3 shows the trend in average Connectivity sub-indicator from 2017 to 2022 in each cluster. In 2017 the average of Connectivity ratio for Clusters 1 was above the ASEAN average, while Cluster 2 and 3 were lower than the ASEAN average. Almost all countries in Cluster 1 and only Thailand in Cluster 2, and none of the countries in Cluster 3 had a connectivity ratio above the ASEAN average. In 2022, the average of Connectivity ratio in Clusters 1, Malaysia was above, and Philippines is almost same to the ASEAN average. while in Cluster 2, Indonesia is near the ASEAN average, while Myanmar is below. in Cluster 3, only Cambodia and Lao P.D.R. were below the ASEAN average.

All clusters had a mixed improvement/decline in the average indicator of connectivity during the period between 2017 and 2022, with Cluster 3 recording the highest increase of more than 315%, followed by decline in Cluster 2 with almost 31%, and Cluster 1 with 21% decline.

Market

The sub-components of the CMG indicator such as Market in 2022 show a decrease of 26.3 % compared to 2017, however its average is below the average value of the aforementioned CMG. Further, as presented in figure 3, the countries with the highest growth rates were Myanmar, while all other countries exhibit decline in the Market ratio and growth.

In 2017, four countries were below the ASEAN average. These countries included Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Lao P.D.R., and Myanmar. Whereas in 2022 it was seven countries such as Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Lao P.D.R., Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, and Vietnam. The lowest scores on the Market indicator in the ASEAN Member States for

Working paper WP2

2017 appeared in Lao P.D.R. with 0.0126 points, Myanmar with 0.0426 points, and Brunei Darussalam with 0.194. While in 2022, it was Lao P.D.R. with 0.0104, Brunei Darussalam with 0.1798 points, and Cambodia with 0.1997. Significantly, for all those countries which had the worst Market rates in 2017, only Myanmar scores improved by 2022 against the ASEAN average.

Conversely, in 2017, six countries were above the ASEAN average. These countries included Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Viet Nam. Whereas in 2022 it was three countries such as Myanmar, Indonesia, and Thailand. The highest scores on the Market indicator in the ASEAN Member States for 2017 appeared in Indonesia with 0.9477 points, Thailand with 0.712, and Malaysia with 0.5901. While in 2022, it was Indonesia with 0.6285 points, Myanmar with 0.5033, and Thailand with 0.4281. Significantly, for all those countries which had the highest Market rates in 2017, their scores against the ASEAN average declined by 2022.

Thus, as shown in the Table 2, comparing the performance of individual countries against the ASEAN average in 2017, it was found that Lao P.D.R. had the lowest rate of 3.5%, while Indonesia had the highest 260 % rate. Similarly, in the 2022, it was found that Lao P.D.R. had the lowest rate of 2.9 %, while Myanmar had the highest 138 % rate.

The fact that the gap between the lowest and highest rates as compared to the ASEAN average has been gradually decreasing from 93.5 pps in 2017 to 61.8 pps in 2022, gives a positive trend toward more convergence across ASEAN countries. This positive trend is further diluted by the countries observation where the value of the relationship between the highest and the lowest rates dropped from 74 in 2017 to a far lower value of 47 in 2022.

Table 3 shows the trend in average Market sub-indicator from 2017 to 2022 in each cluster. In 2017 the average Market ratio for Clusters 1 and 2 was above the ASEAN average, while Cluster 3 was lower than the ASEAN average. Singapore and Malaysia in Cluster 1, all country in Cluster 2, and none of the countries in Cluster 3 had a Market ratio above the ASEAN average. In 2022 the average Market ratio for only Clusters 2 was above the ASEAN average. Additionally, none of the countries in Cluster 1, Indonesia and Myanmar in Cluster 2, and Thailand in cluster 3, had a Market ratio above the ASEAN average.

All clusters had a mixed improvement/decline in the average indicator of Market during the period between 2017 and 2022, with Cluster 3 recording the highest increase of more than 137%, followed by decline in Cluster 2 with almost 14%, and Cluster 1 with 39% decline.

Governance, Affordability, Sustainability and Trust (GAST)

The sub-components of the CMG indicator, such as GAST indicator in 2022 show an increase of 3.9% compared to 2017, however its average is above the average value of the aforementioned CMG. Further, as presented in figure 3, the countries with the positive growth rates were Lao P.D.R., Thailand, Malaysia, and Cambodia respectively, while other countries experienced negative growth.

Working paper WP2

In 2017, four countries were below the ASEAN average. These countries included Cambodia, Lao P.D.R., Myanmar, and Thailand. Whereas in 2022 it was six countries such as Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Lao P.D.R., Myanmar, Thailand, and Vietnam. The lowest scores on the GAST indicator in the ASEAN Member States for 2017 appeared in Lao P.D.R. with 0.3189 points, Thailand with 0.4908, and Myanmar with 0.5084. While in 2022, it was Myanmar with 0.4797, Cambodia with 0.5333, and Brunei Darussalam with 0.5751. Significantly, for all those countries which had the worst GAST rates in 2017, their scores against the ASEAN average improved, but not above ASEAN average by 2022.

Conversely, in 2017, six countries were above the ASEAN average. These countries included Brunei Darussalam, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, and Vietnam. Whereas in 2022 it was 3 countries such as Philippines, Singapore, and Indonesia. The highest scores on the GAST indicator in the ASEAN Member States for 2017 appeared in Singapore with 0.8793 points, Brunei Darussalam with 0.7759, and Malaysia with 0.7244. While in 2022, it was Singapore with 0.9696 points, Malaysia with 0.8669, and Philippines with 0.8393. Significantly, for all those countries which had the highest GAST rates in 2017, their scores against the ASEAN average declined by 2022, except for Malaysia.

Thus, as shown in the Table 2, comparing the performance of individual countries against the ASEAN average in 2017, it was found that Lao P.D.R. had the lowest rate of 47.47%, while Singapore had the highest 130 % rate. Similarly, in the 2022, it was found that Myanmar had the lowest rate of 71 %, while Malaysia had the highest 148.8 % rate.

The fact that the gap between the lowest and highest rates as compared to the ASEAN average has been gradually decreasing from 56 pps in 2017 to 52 pps in 2022, gives a positive trend toward more convergence across ASEAN countries. This positive trend is further diluted by the countries observation where the value of the relationship between the highest and the lowest rates dropped from 2.8 in 2017 to a far lower value of 2.1 in 2022.

Table 3 shows the trend in average GAST sub-indicator from 2017 to 2022 in each cluster. In 2017 the average GAST ratio for Clusters 1 and 2 were above the ASEAN average, while Cluster 3 was lower than the ASEAN average. Almost all countries in Cluster 1 and except Thailand in Cluster 2, and none of the countries in Cluster 3, had a GAST ratio above the ASEAN average. In 2022 the average GAST ratio for only Clusters 1 was above the ASEAN average. Additionally, Indonesia and Philippine in Cluster 1, Indonesia in Cluster 2, and Singapore in cluster 3, had a GAST ratio above the ASEAN average.

All clusters had a mixed improvement/decline in the average indicator of GEST during the period between 2017 and 2022, with Cluster 3 recording the highest increase of more than 43%, followed by Cluster 1 with almost 10 % increase, and Cluster 2 with 15% decline.

Working paper WP2

5. Conclusions

It should be emphasized that the implementation of scientific research in the area of “The Assessment of the State of the Digital Economy in South-East Asia” allowed to achieve the main goal of the article and thanks to the conducted research it was possible to analyze and assess the level of digitization of Southeast Asian countries, indicating their similarities and differences and presenting appropriate conclusions. Thanks to this publication preparation, a research gap was identified, which indicated the lack of research on the level of digitization of Southeast Asian countries and the similarity of structures in this area. The achievement of this article is not only the identification of a research gap, but above all, this research gap has been filled and the research problem presented in the form of a question “*Are the digitalisation levels of Southeast Asian countries similar or are there specific differences between them and, if so, are they significant?*” has been solved, also by verifying the hypotheses.

The objects of the research were the following Southeast Asian countries: Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Indonesia, Lao PDR, Malaysia, Myanmar (Burma), Philippines, Singapore, Thailand and Vietnam, which together form one region centered around the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN).). The choice of ASEAN countries was not accidental, but is related to their increasing importance and the role they play in the world economy (over 8% of the world's population and almost 4% share in the GDP of the world economy in 2024). The time scope of the research covered the period 2017-2022, which was adopted due to the availability of data on the analysis and assessment of the level of digitalization of the analyzed economies of the ASEAN countries.

It can therefore be pointed out that the main catalysts for economic growth in ASEAN are improved ICT infrastructure combined with technology-related demographic advantages. For ASEAN countries, the digital economy is crucial to driving digital transformation, which creates enormous opportunities for economic growth and development. The use of digital transformation between countries is also changing the shape of global trade through, among others, innovations in e-commerce. Digital transformation has also accelerated due to the challenges posed by the Covid-19 pandemic, which have spurred digital innovation around the world, including in the ASEAN region.

However, a major issue in ASEAN's digital transformation is the growing digital divide both within and between countries. Southeast Asia is working to close the digital divide characterized by unequal access to and use of information and communication technologies (ICT). This gap affecting connectivity, access, utilization and skills hinders rapid economic growth and technological progress in the region. ASEAN countries experience various digital divides, including disparities in Internet speed, use and technology production. Factors such as socioeconomic status, education, geographic location and cultural attitudes play a key role in shaping individuals' access to and proficiency in using digital technologies. Strengthening regional cooperation through initiatives such as the ASEAN Digital Integration Framework will

Working paper WP2

be key. While significant progress has been made in ASEAN, challenges such as the digital divide, cybersecurity and regulatory issues remain to be addressed.

Summarizing the conclusions drawn from the literature analysis, it can be concluded that research on the level of digitalization of Southeast Asian countries and the identification of structural similarities is very limited. Therefore, the implementation of this research in this article was even more justified, thanks to which this research gap was filled.

The implementation of this research required the authors to develop an innovative and pioneering research methodology in this field. Taking into account the selected research method, consistent with the adopted aim of the work and other conceptual assumptions, a selection of data was made that was used for calculations using the above-mentioned research method. For this purpose, data was downloaded from the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) database. There are as many as 178 indicators available in the ITU database, which is why they have been verified and divided into three basic research areas, which are called:

- 1) Communication Area
- 2) Market Area
- 3) Governance, Affordability, Sustainability and Trust (GAST) Area.

Moreover, an undoubted achievement of the conducted research is the development of the main synthetic indicator, called CMG indicator (the name comes from the first letters of the area names), as well as partial synthetic indicators: Connectivity Indicator, Market Indicator and GAST Indicator. With regard to the research method, a taxonomic grouping of similarities was selected to assess the structures of the digitization level of ASEAN countries. In this respect, the choice concerned the clustering method. It should be emphasized that the innovative research methodology developed by the authors assumes the use of quantitative and qualitative methods, which involves the triangulation of research methods and allows for higher quality of the research and reduction of measurement error.

The research made it possible to verify the research hypotheses.

Hypothesis 1 was positively verified, where the research shows significant differences in the Southeast Asian region (ASEAN) not only in terms of the level of socio-economic development but also in the level of digitalization of individual countries in this region, which allowed for the separation of individual groups in the form of so-called clusters. In 2017, three clusters were identified among ASEAN countries and the grouping showed that each cluster included countries with a very similar level of socio-economic development and competitiveness. However, the grouping carried out in 2022 indicates the separation of 3 clusters within which greater differentiation can be indicated, which indicates changes in ICT indicators for the ASEAN region.

Based on the research conducted, hypothesis 2 was also positively verified and it can be indicated that among ASEAN countries there are groups of countries with high, medium and low levels of digitalization compared to the entire region. This was shown by the analysis of the values achieved by the CMG indicator in the analyzed years 2017 and 2022, three of the ASEAN countries achieved a result below the average, while seven countries in ASEAN

Working paper WP2

achieved a result above the average. Below average countries in both 2017 and 2022 were Cambodia, Lao P.D.R. and Myanmar. Countries with above-average CMG values in both years included Brunei Darussalam, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Thailand, Viet Nam, and Singapore. Analysis of the CMG indicator at the national level highlighted several changes between the two years covered by the study. These changes are positive and indicate an increase in the development of CMG.

Hypothesis 3, however, was partially positively verified, because research in relation to Vietnam showed that when comparing GDP per capita in ASEAN in 2017-2022, it can be indicated that Vietnam was among the countries with the lowest GDP per capita value. However, the results of the cluster analysis indicate that Vietnam belongs to cluster 2, together with countries such as Indonesia, Philippines, Thailand, with moderate similarity and at different levels of ICT development. In 2022, Vietnam is also in Cluster 3, which is the most diverse. Vietnam was also among countries with above-average CMG values in both years included, Brunei Darussalam, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Thailand, and Singapore. So Vietnam, despite having one of the lowest GDP per capita, is not one of the countries with the lowest level of economy digitalization.

Results of the research and analysis of the dynamics of Average CMGs' Individual Sub-rates in 2017–2022 show that the average CMG increased only in the 3rd cluster by 76 %, putting Clusters 3 in positions of great momentum between the years 2017 and 2022. The sub-components of the CMG indicator also present interesting findings. As such, Connectivity and GAST in 2022, show an increases compared to 2017. The sub-components of the CMG indicator, as such Market in 2022 show a decrease compared to 2017, however its average is below the average value of the aforementioned CMG. The country level analysis of the CMG indicator has outlined several changes between the two surveyed years. These changes are positive and show an increase in the CMG development.

This research on the level of digitalization of ASEAN countries is clearly pioneering taking into account the methodological approach for data and indicators from the ITU's Database. They fill the identified research gap, which is confirmed by the literature review in this thematic area carried out in the first step. The novelty of the research is visible primarily in the analysis and assessment carried out, along with drawing conclusions and presenting them, based on data and indicators from the ITU database, selected through expert selection along with the development of a synthetic main indicator and partial synthetic indicators developed by the article's authors.

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